

Constant Velocity in Terms of x/t or $1/(x \text{ resolution}) / 1/(\text{time resolution})$

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Velocity in Newtonian mechanics is defined (in one dimension) by dx/dt . For a constant velocity passing through $x=0, t=0$, one has $x/t=v$. If v is not 0, the particle moves through different amounts of x space relative to t space. If one treats x and ct on the same footing, where c is a constant to make the units of x and ct the same, then one might ask: How can one have a velocity in the first place and still preserve equal footing of x and t (i.e. have equal lengths for x and t)?

We suggest one consider different t and x resolutions. In such a case, $x=1$ and $ct=1$, but $v = (1/x \text{ resolution}) / (1/\text{time resolution})$. If x and t resolutions differ, these may be linked to different properties of the particle which create these resolutions. The question is: What are these properties?

We argue that one may try to find these properties by considering results from special relativity. If one has a particle with rest mass, m_0 , then one has: $E = \gamma m_0 c^2$ and $p = \gamma m_0 v$ ($c=1$) and $E = m_0/\sqrt{1-v^2}$ and $p = m_0 v/\sqrt{1-v^2}$. For $v \rightarrow 1$ (i.e. c), $E=p$ for the first equation and the combination of the second and third. Thus, for $v=c$ (the speed of light), E and p take on the same value for $c=1$. Using $E=pc$ for $m_0=0$, time resolution would be $1/E$ and spatial resolution $1/p$. If one considers an $m_0 \neq 0$ in the rest frame, then $1/m_0$ would be temporal resolution and $1/p$, where $p=0$ would be spatial. $1/0 \rightarrow$ infinite suggesting an infinite range of x .

For a finite v , one would have $(1 / (1/E)) / (1 / (1/p))$. This suggests that temporal resolution is $1/E$ (or \hbar/E with $\hbar=1$) and spatial, $1/p$ (or \hbar/p). If one assigns dt to temporal resolution and dx to spatial, then $-E dt + p dx = 0$, or $A = -Et+px$ which should be a Lorentz invariant.

Thus, we argue that there are two ways to think of a constant velocity. One is the usual x/t (for a particle passing through $x=0, t=0$) and the other is a notion in which lengths in space and time (x and ct) are the same, but one has different spatial and time resolutions which account for the sense of velocity. Both of these are compatible with special relativity. The resolution definition of velocity, however, has physical consequences because a particle would not be able to resolve two slits separated by about \hbar/p while a person with a ruler with resolution greater than \hbar/p would. Thus, the particle should interact with each slit in a probabilistic manner, i.e. through quantum mechanics.

The Notion of Velocity

In Newtonian mechanics, velocity in one dimension is defined by: $v = dx/dt$ ((1)).

For a particle with constant velocity passing through $x=0, t=0$, $v = x/t$ ((2)).

((2)) holds also in special relativity for a constant velocity (passing through $x=0, t=0$).

Special relativity, however, is supposed to treat time ct and space on the same footing, so why should a particle travel different lengths in each, i.e. $x/t=v$? We suggest that if ct and x are on the

same footing, i.e. one ultimately has the same length (we use 1) for both time and space. If that is the case, how can one have a velocity? We suggest that there may exist different temporal and spatial resolutions. In such a case, we one dimensional velocity as:

$$V = (1/\text{space resolution}) / (1/\text{time resolution}) \quad ((3))$$

This begs the question: What are these resolutions?

Special Relativity

In special relativity $v = \text{constant} = x/t$ for a particle passing through $x=0, t=0$. At first glance, there are no spatial and temporal resolutions. We consider the results:

$$((4)) \quad E^2 = p^2 + m^2 \quad (c=1) \quad \text{and} \quad ((5)) \quad E = m/\sqrt{1-v^2} \quad \text{and} \quad p = mv / \sqrt{1-v^2}$$

If $m=0$ in ((4)), one has $E=p$ for $c=1$. In ((5)), if $v=c$, one has $E=p$ as well.

We suggest that $E=pc$ is consistent with:

$$\text{Time resolution} = 1/E \quad \text{and} \quad \text{spatial resolution} = 1/p \quad ((6)) \quad (\text{Here we use } \hbar=1)$$

$E=pc$, however, only holds for a photon with rest mass $m=0$, or for $v=c$ for $m \neq 0$.

What about $v < c$? If ((6)) is to hold, then:

$$Dt (\text{resolution}) = 1/E \quad \text{and} \quad dx (\text{resolution}) = 1/p \quad ((7))$$

$$((7)) \text{ implies that: } -Edt + pdx = 0 \quad ((8))$$

((8)) means that: $A = -Et+px$, where A is a constant. This result should hold in all frames so A is a Lorentz invariant, as it is.

As a result, we suggest that special relativity accommodates two different ways of looking at a constant velocity which passes through $x=0, t=0$.

The first way is the usual $v=x/t$, but the second way treats time and space lengths as equivalent and changes the temporal and spatial resolutions, i.e. uses \hbar/E and \hbar/p . Given that E and p are properties of the particle, these resolutions are tied to the particle itself and allow the particle to sense velocity by having different resolutions.

This physically suggests that a particle with momentum p has dx resolution of \hbar/p . This means that it cannot sharply distinguish between two slits which are about \hbar/p apart even though an external ruler with spatial resolution much sharper than \hbar/p can. From the point of view of the external ruler, the particle should pass through one slit or the other, but the particle itself cannot discern the two slits and interaction becomes a probabilistic one involving both slits. In other words, the particle's internal spatial resolution causes it to interact with both slits.

How does one go from dx and dt resolutions to the notion of probability? We suggest that a resolution length of \hbar/p means that one has a uniform distribution $p(x)$, but this is repeated periodically. One needs a probability function $P_1(p(x))$ such that $P_1(p_1(x))P_1(p_2(x)) = P_1((p_1+p_2)(x))$ and $\exp(ipx)$ is a solution. Thus, the second (resolution) way of regarding velocity leads to free particle quantum mechanics.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that special relativity allows one to regard velocity (constant, one dimensional) in two ways. For a particle passing through $x=0, t=0$, one has the usual $v=x/t$, but if one wishes to have space and time on the same footing, one would argue for $x=1$ and $ct=1$, where c is a constant which converts t to a length. If one has equal x and t units, then to have a velocity, we suggest different time and spatial resolutions, i.e. $v = (1/\text{space resolution}) / (1/\text{time resolution})$.

We suggest that these resolutions may be obtained by examining $E^2 = p^2 + m_0^2$ for $m_0=0$ and $m_0/\sqrt{1-v^2}$ and $mv/\sqrt{1-v^2}$ ($c=1$). For $v=1$ (i.e. c), one has $E=p$ just as in the $m_0=0$ case. In other words, in both cases, $E=pc$, suggesting that $c=x/t = (1 / (1/E)) / (1 / (1/p))$. Thus, time resolution = $1/E$ (or \hbar/E) and spatial resolution: $1/p$ (or \hbar/p). If this is to hold in general for $m_0 \neq 0$, then $-E dt + p dx = 0$. Here dt and dx are the resolutions. This implies that $A = -Et + px$ is a constant, i.e. a Lorentz invariant which it is. (Note: dx/dt is not velocity here, dx and dt are resolutions.)

In other words, we suggest that there are two different ways in special relativity to define constant velocity (through $x=0, t=0$). The resolution approach, however, has physical consequences because the particle can only resolve \hbar/E in time and \hbar/p in space. This means that if one has two slits separated by about \hbar/p , the particle cannot resolve these, while a person using a ruler with higher spatial resolution than \hbar/p can. We suggest that the particle must interact with both slits in a probabilistic manner. The probability used is based on the uniform distribution $p(x)$ (resolution) which appears in a periodic manner. This periodic manner $P_1(p(x))$ must satisfy $P_1(p_1(x))P_1(p_2(x)) = P_1((p_1+p_2)(x))$ or $P_1(p(x)) = \exp(ipx)$, giving rise to free particle quantum mechanics.